

ASSESSMENT OF THE KNOWLEDGE OF LANGUAGE LEARNERS

M.Kakharova

(Fergana State University, professor)

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Abstract: in this article, the evaluation of the knowledge levels of language learners, the types of evaluation, the researches based on them and their analysis are discussed in detail.

Key words: level of knowledge, assessment, planning, design, test, exam, certificate, ÖSD, TestDaF, Cambridge exam, TOEFL, IELTS, formal exam, informal exam, summative (final) assessment, formative assessment.

It is known that, one of the main responsibilities of teachers is to check and analysis the students` proficiency level of knowledge consciously or unconsciously as well as in a formal or informal way. The results of the assessment are released to the language learners. However, in European countries, the results can be sent not only students, but also their parents. This can help to conduct and organize a language learning easier. Assessment is considered as an integral part of teachers` profession.

In the following, we will be informed about important types of assessing and testing students` knowledge. Knowing these types can lead to assess our testing process effectively. It can be seen that if we are able to differentiate the types of assessment, we could create an effective environment to assess in our practical teaching.

It is not a secret that tests and exams are formal types of assessing the knowledge. These types of assessment require much more effort from teachers. For example, Goethe of the institute certificate exams, Austria language diploma exams (ÖSD), german language test as a foreign language (TestDaF) or Cambridge exams , such as TOEFL or IELTS English language tests can be included. Official exams should be matched with needs of specific standards and criteria.

On the other hand, informal exams and tests are easier process by requiring less effort than formal ones. But it should be appropriate for the standards of quality. Different classroom tests and exams conducted by teachers in order to acknowledge can be example for informal assessment.

One of the features of formal assessment is being standardized. The main purpose of standardization is to provide the assessment comparison process with the authentic and fair results. In the standardized assessment, the types of assignments, their appropriateness for the students` level and age are discussed.

If we try and assess our knowledge in any standardized exams, such as Goethe or TestDaF exams, we can realize the importance and rules of using this practice. After passing the exams, we can achieve different certificates that represent our whole score or grades. These grading systems can be different according to test system. (for example, B1 or A2)

In most cases, exams and assessment can be takes with the help of other results. Such kind of approach can be called as a directed evaluation to the appropriate groups or directed to the

norm. _ However, this kind of evaluation may cause a problem. Evaluating the exam results as " good " or " bad " belongs to the group work level and difficulty of exam questions as it is observed . This kind of evaluation can occur in teachers` evaluation process in practice, for example , we are going to choose a candidate in order to get a scholarship to Germany, this candidate`s result does not mean that she or he is able to perform all language skills in an linguistic action compared to others.

Mostly, language learners would like to be assessed relatively by focusing on how to work in groups. In this case, additional assessment, which is based on assigned standards, can be conducted. This type of evaluation can be called as criterial assessment. The evaluation can assess the students` vocabulary and their word choice to the different context. This evaluation is absolute since it does not depend on working on groups, but the importance of meaning and context. The authenticity of the evaluation should be regarded in this case. Because, there is motivation manner in assessing language learners. If all language learners are assessed with the help of the same norms, it can have a negative influence on their motivation. In order to prevent this, teacher can assess the special features of students` knowledge in evaluation or can give additional bonus or scores. Moreover, teacher can keep the differential evaluation in informal assessment or use different approaches for assessing based on their different interests or degree.

In order to assess, teacher can use summative assessment as a final result of the course or formative assessment which can be integrated in the learning process permanently. Usually, it is not easy to differentiate between summative and formative assessment. This difference depends on the purpose of using the assessment in the learning.

Summative (Final) assessment can be conducted in any educational settings, such as school or university as an inner or outer assessment by taking all the responsibilities of social norms. This assessment can be organized in order to know the students` acquisition based on important standards form the course, semester or the whole year. So, summative assessment is focused on identifying the quality og given knowledge in particular period and can be planned to grade, assign to other courses or choose an appropriate candidate. For that reason, summative assessment can regarded as assessment of learning, particularly the success of learning in most English works.

In the formative assessment, the results are addressed in order to organize the future lessons. This evaluation can help the lesson develop and improve the students` practice and knowledge. So, it can be called as learning assessment or assessment in learning purpose. The main feature o this assessment is an observation.

Formative assessment is usually assigned to some standard norms and it can avoid from comparing students from each other. Furthermore, if the purpose of learning and assessment norms are clear, both teachers and students have to take responsibilities for the results. In the summative assessment, candidate or student can achieve higher and broader results than formative assessment. Especially, any diagnostic form conducted in the learning process can be an example for formative assessment. For example, when learner is doing any assignment and cannot remember, speak about past, teacher can prepare and use different approaches in order to help thus learner in the next lessons. This will be formative assessment. Compared to standardized assessment, formative assessment is not planned beforehand, it can automatically occur during the lesson as dialogue between a teacher and student or pair-work. In the formative assessment, learners should speak about their strengths and

weaknesses or solve the problems when they are facing. Usually, this should not be graded, rather it should help to improve students' motivation for learning.

If we conduct some particular formative tests, we can be aware of the dynamic of improving students' language proficiency skills. Nowadays, language competencies of learners can be developed in a dynamic way, as their language is also dynamic structure.

Based on the opinions above, we can differentiate formative and summative assessment with 5 features.

Formative assessment	Summative assessment
Assessment can be conducted during the lesson permanently	Assessment can be conducted at the end of the course.
Assessment can be interactive or organized as a dialogue or pair and group work	Assessment can be organized in a written or spoken format
The results of assessment can be used in order to develop the lesson by a teacher.	The results of assessment can be used in order to identify the achievement of students during the course.
The results of learners can be used in order to improve the acknowledgement logically.	The final results can be used as a part of identifying the quality of students.
Usually, it is not connected with different perspectives	Final results are connected with different perspectives.

As a conclusion, it is important to assess the knowledge of language learners based on different norms and approaches permanently.

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